

TECHNOLOGIES OF IMPLEMENTATION OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: In the article is considered some aspects of distance learning technology introduction into higher educational institutions.

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Today, in the current conditions where the demand for highly qualified pedagogic personnel is increasing, it is necessary to train pedagogic personnel as personnel who have thoroughly mastered modern pedagogical and information technologies. The implementation of such tasks consists in improving the existing system of improving the qualifications of public education workers, developing it based on the requirements of electronic education, solidly acquiring fundamental knowledge in the field of specialization in public education institutions, and establishing various forms of professional development. It requires a lifelong orientation to education based on the principle of "reading". In this sense, improving the professional qualifications of public education workers and retraining them has a special place in the continuous education system of our republic. The main goal of this is to constantly improve and improve the general outlook and professional skills of pedagogic personnel.

Today, many teachers directly use interactive methods, innovative pedagogical and information technologies in the course of the lesson. In this way, the teacher spends less effort during the lesson and achieves efficiency by providing more information, and the students see it with their eyes and keep it in their memory for a long time.

In education, these technologies that teach students to independently search for acquired knowledge, to study and analyze independently, to identify their mistakes and draw conclusions, are joint activities of the student and the teacher. If information technologies are used in the implementation of this activity, the retention of knowledge will increase. These are, in particular, a computer, a video projector, an overhead projector, a smart TV, an interactive whiteboard.

If the presentation of a new topic is made in the form of an electronic textbook or video clips, the possibility of remembering information increases. Because the ability of the organs of vision to remember information is higher than the organs of hearing. This, in turn, allows the visual system to deliver about 90% of the information received by the pupil, and as a result, cognitive activity is accelerated. The first 20 minutes of reading are the most effective, and after 30 minutes, motivation to continue reading begins to wane rapidly.

These suggestions serve to keep the reader's attention for longer and keep them well in their memory. The more sensory channels are used in the process of perception, the higher the quantity and quality of remembered knowledge. If knowledge is given only through a lecture (through passive listening), after 3 days it is possible to remember only 25% of it. If it is conducted by lecturing (listening), showing and demonstrating (seeing, holding, etc.) and discussing, then after 3 days it is possible to achieve 75% memorization.

If several sensory channels are used together in the perception of knowledge, the process of transferring information from short memory to long memory, which is the basis of perception, is accelerated.

The degree of influence of teaching methods on the level of students' mastery:

1. Lecture - 5% of the information we heard.
2. Reading - 10% of what we read.
3. Video method, demonstration - 20% of what we see.
4. Demonstration of experience - 30% of what we see and hear.
5. Discussion - 40% of what we discuss.
6. Exercises - 50% of what we read, write, speak.
7. Business game, working in small groups, designing - 75% of what we studied independently, analyzed and discussed, defended and demonstrated.
8. Reference text, problem situation, teaching others - 90% of the theories we learned independently, analyzed and discussed, taught to others remain in memory.

Year after year, the 21st century shows that it was not given such a name as the age of information technologies. Such changes affect the organization and conduct of educational processes. One of such changes is the rapid introduction of multimedia lessons into the educational system.

What is multimedia itself:

Multimedia is a multi-channel way of presenting information (text, image, animation, audio, video). That is, the quality of the information given during the lesson is presented to the student based on technical means. Multimedia can be explained as follows.

Multimedia recordings are collections of publications, displays, visual images, animations and audio files placed on compact discs or other computer data carriers, as well as on devices that provide users with access at any time.

Multimedia environment is a technology that provides a comprehensive (complex) description of arbitrary types of media, providing joint processing of images (including animation - movement), speech, sound and documents.

Multimedia textbooks are textbooks on laser discs with high-order dynamics of visual materials using multimedia media.

Multimedia technology is a method of preparing electronic documents, which includes the unified control of interactive software, visual and audio - efficient, multi-programming of various situations.

The main condition for understanding and passing multimedia lessons is to be able to use technical tools, especially to know how to work with a computer. For them, it is necessary to know how to work with the Power Point presentation editor application package, create visual material and present them. When creating multimedia slides, you should pay attention to the following: the idea given on the slide should not exceed six lines. Often we try to display the entire page of text on the screen. However, most people do not read such slides. Metadata should be used as widely as possible.

Metadata - short information identifiers (indexes, keywords) designed to describe the meaning of information data (text, image, table, etc.).

- ❖ It is not recommended to use colors and animations that tire the eyes when placing information;

- ❖ It is recommended to use video, music, pictures on the topic, taking into account motivation;

So, today we are proud to live in the age of high technology, but we must admit that information attacks are increasing due to inappropriate use of these technologies by some evil forces. Our activities to protect our society from the flow of destructive and destructive information, especially to protect the integrity of the spiritual world

of our youth, to form a culture of using the Internet network, state bodies, public organizations, information security and protection from cyber attacks, our own - is implemented by self-governing bodies. Citizens' state bodies, all institutions of civil society, pedagogues and specialists call for long-term continuous and systematic cooperation, of course.

The introduction of modern information and communication technologies into the educational process led to the emergence of a new form - distance education, in addition to traditional teaching methods. Why is it necessary to create the theoretical basis for the introduction of information technologies in education, to create and implement distance education courses? First, the teacher is becoming one of the sources of knowledge acquisition, not as an organizer of the educational process, and secondly, at the stage of development of science and technology, there is a sharp increase in information and the limitation of time to use it. in the educational process, as well as the requirements of excellent preparation of students for professional activities, require the introduction of modern technologies into the educational system. Fundamental changes in the field of education in our country require the development of methodical provision of the educational process in every educational institution.

In the education of information and communication technologies, students are spatially separated from each other and constantly communicate with each other with the help of specially created training courses, control forms, electronic communication and other technologies of the Internet. Distance education based on the use of Internet technologies provides access to the global information-educational network, performs new functions based on the principle of integration and interaction.

Information and communication technologies provide an opportunity for those who want to study education to constantly improve their skills. In the course of such

training, the student learns independent educational-methodological materials in an interactive mode, passes control, performs control work directly under the guidance of the teacher, communicates with other members of the virtual learning group in the group. The use of ICT is mainly carried out in two ways.

The first condition is technical equipment, the second condition is provision of special software:

1. Provision of technical equipment: computers, network devices, high-speed Internet networks, video conference communication equipment, etc.
2. Software includes a collection of programs, systems and platforms designed for this industry.

Educational process management systems play a key role in the organization of distance education. Teaching is a systematic and recursive process. All participants and objects involved in the same teaching scenarios should unite in the direction of intellectual activity by sharing knowledge and forming expert evaluations. In addition, they should be able to share information with each other through various media. Thus, it is important to build different teaching processes based on different teaching subjects and objects.

Wide implementation of modern information and communication technologies, in particular, the introduction of distance education courses based on educational management systems. These are:

- Informatization of scientific fields;
- Intellectualization of educational activities;
- Deepening the processes of integration of participants in the educational system;

▪ It leads to the improvement of the infrastructure of the educational system and its management mechanisms. Effective organization of pedagogical education processes based on modern information technologies;

▪ Uniting educators, computer programmers, relevant specialists into a team creating distance education courses and electronic literature;

Broad introduction of distance education into the qualification system:

- Acquiring modern professional knowledge;
- Deep mastery of the field of science by modeling the studied phenomena and processes;

- Expanding the field of independent activity of the pedagogue due to the diverse organization of educational activities;

- Individualization and differentiation of the teaching process based on the introduction of interactive communication opportunities;

- Mastering the strategy of mastering pedagogical educational materials using the capabilities of the artificial intelligence system;

- Formation of information culture as a member of the information society;

- Presenting the studied processes and phenomena with the help of computer technologies is of great importance as it increases the interest and activity of students in the basics of science.

Therefore, one of the necessary conditions for improving the content of education is to increase the opportunities for independent learning of students, to create conditions for the formation and development of electronic information resources of education.

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